

ICF - INFORMED CONSENT FORM

STUDY: Anonymous Application Image Capture Optimization

You are being invited to participate in the study mentioned above. The information below contains all the necessary information about our study. Your collaboration in this study will be of great importance to us.

By signing this term, I freely and voluntarily agree to participate in the study "Optimization of Image Capture in the Anonymous Application", and I clarify that I obtained all the information. I am aware that:

- I. The study is necessary to validate and identify improvements to the prototype of the initial requirements proposed for the application of Anonymous;
- II. This study's general objective is to understand how to optimize the capture process to make things faster and more functional based on teachers' reality.
- III. As a study methodology, brainstorming will be carried out, with an estimated time of 2 (two) hours;
- IV. Participants will carry out activities in person, in the city of Anônimo, individually, with the moderation of the researcher Anônimo;
- V. Participants will be introduced to the current version of the application for contextualization;
- VI. Before the activities, you will be invited to answer some characterization questions, which will be answered through a questionnaire;
- VII. During the activities, you will present solutions through physical material that will be made available;
- VIII. The benefits of your participation involve collaboration to advance the project in question, as well as carrying out activities that will contribute to your learning and development;
- IX. Participation in this study does not involve physical risks. However, it is possible that the participant may feel embarrassed when participating;
- X. I am free to withdraw or interrupt collaboration in this study whenever I wish, without the need for any explanation;
- XI. The results obtained during this study will be kept confidential, but I agree that they will be disclosed in scientific publications or reports as long as personal data that allows me to be identified is not mentioned;
- XII. If I wish, I will be able to learn about the results at the end of this research by contacting those responsible for the research;

The data collected will be stored under Anonymous's responsibility and under Anonymous's custody.

If you have any doubts about the ethical aspects of this study, you can consult:

Responsible for the study: Anonymous

Email: Anonymous